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THE TENSIONS BETWEEN THE USA AND IRAN

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***Annotation.** Throughout all international relations, the United States has been trying to interact with all the countries except one nation called the Islamic Republic of Iran and the tensions between these two countries were very harsh because of the fact that there was a situation that took place known as the infamous Iran Hostage Crisis the United States has decided not to open a single U.S. Embassy in that country. After all of these years, the conflict remains the same strained. But why is this the case? Is it all necessary? Although, historically the US had an awful relationship with Iran because of the deceit, and covert operations, the US now has a great chance to ease the harsh ties between these two nations. If both nations reconcile the past, it could provide a fruitful future.*

***Keywords:** the United States, Islamic Republic of Iran, Mohammed Mosaddegh, British authorities, Iranian Revolution, Oil.*

НАПРЯЖЕННОСТЬ МЕЖДУ США И ИРАНОМ

***Аннотация.** На протяжении всех международных отношений Соединенные Штаты пытались взаимодействовать со всеми странами, кроме одной страны, называемой Исламской Республикой Иран, и напряженность между этими двумя странами была очень жесткой из-за того, что произошла ситуация, известная как печально известный Иранский кризис с заложниками, Соединенные Штаты решили не открывать ни одного посольства США в этой стране. После всех этих лет конфликт остается таким же напряженным. Но почему это так? Необходимо ли все это? Хотя исторически у США были ужасные отношения с Ираном из-за обмана и тайных операций, у США теперь*

есть отличный шанс смягчить жесткие связи между этими двумя странами. Если обе страны примирят прошлое, это может обеспечить плодотворное будущее.

Ключевые слова: США, Исламская Республика Иран, Мохаммед Мосаддык, британские власти, Иранская революция, нефть.

Introduction. As mentioned above, the relations between the United States and the Islamic Republic of Iran have been noted as strained through the years. The first conflict happened in 1953 and this does not mean that these two countries had relations before it means that the first covert operation took place in 1953. This trend marked a turning point in the balance of the nation's affairs and the nature of the country's relationships. The former correspondent of The Boston Globe and the New York Times magazine Stephen Kinzer in his book named "Overthrow" mentions the currents of nationalism and anti-colonialism moved to Asia, Africa, and South America. Idealistic Iranian leader Mohammad Mosaddegh came into power in 1951. Mohammad Mosaddegh's main goal was to achieve modernization and democracy within the country and for that reason, the main goals of the new prime minister and the nation's monarch Mohammad Reza Shah were significantly different from each other. Then he started to focus on British oil giant BP WITH natural resources whose revenues were under another country and he chose to nationalize it. Seeing that the country's oil is run by foreign institutions he declared that he would nationalize the country's oil and keep it for its population. The law that would help to nationalize countries' oil was declared unanimously by both houses of the Iranian Parliament. Without a doubt, the BP and even the British government were furious with these currents. Persian oil is so vital to our economy said British Foreign Secretary Herbert Morrison. He believes that we try to do our best to keep the contract intake and prevent it from breaching. Over the next few months, the British authorities decided that Mohammad Mosaddegh had to go and start to think about how to overthrow him from his current profession by brainstorming ideas. They tried several times to get back to the Islamic Republic of Iran but after the failed attempts the British agent Christopher Woodhouse reached Washington for help. Christopher Woodhouse made another plan to overthrow Mosaddegh since he knew that American authorities would not take an interest in this current because Time magazine had just named Mosaddegh "Man of the Year". Secretary of State John Dulles and Woodhouse figured out that they could present Mosaddegh's rule as Communist infiltration. This, however, could not have been true. Mohammad Mosaddegh was not really interested in Communist doctrine and did not allow them in his government. With the help of CIA agents such as Kermit Roosevelt and John Dulles, covert operations began in order to overthrow the prime

minister Mohammad Mosaddegh. For weeks the riots had continued in Tehran by local gangs that were paid money by American CIA. Because of the hard situation that had been going on in the streets of Iran, many people claimed Mosaddegh's resignation. Then General Zahedi claimed that he was the new prime minister that had been selected by monarch Shah and he was the new prime minister while Mosaddegh was sitting in jail as all his supporters and himself could not stand a chance against Zahedi's troops. After successfully ousting Mosaddegh the Shah returned to his throne and his new prime minister felt safe. And now the Shah was free to rule the country how he wanted because after the period that he returned to his throne he even created a secret police known as "Savak" to ensure his safety. Through the next three periods It was the times when Iran and US started to interact closely even being the close ally of US in Cold War.

Literature review. The topic known as US and Iran relations the searchers tried to mention the history of these two nations and what was the reason for not having that official diplomatic relations in most cases. The historians write a lot about the bravery of the former prime minister Mohammed Mosaddegh and their efforts to nationalize the country's biggest profitable oil revenue which belonged to BP British institution. He served as prime minister two years In 1951-1953 in the government but in these years he was able to nationalize Iran's oil industry over the British monopoly. However, this article focuses more on the famous Iran Hostage Crisis. Under **Ayatollah Ruhollah Khomeini** the Shah of Iran had to flee to the US since the situation was very escalating. On November 4 a group of students got to the embassy and smashed everything holding 52 hostages captive. That situation obviously, had a negative impact on the United States, and the population of the US was also a little shocked. After the intervention of the Iranian military, the situation was eased and those 52 hostage returned safely to their home country after being captives for 444 days.

Methodology. This study mainly investigates the political and economic conflict between the United States and The Islamic Republic of Iran that arose from 1951 to 1979. As mentioned before one of the closest allies of the United States was Iran during the Cold War and these periods. So, thus, this research contains primary and secondary historical sources. "All The Shah's Men", "Going to Tehran", and "The Twilight War" are considered the main historical sources for the negative relationships of these two. Historical sources such as "The Iranian Revolution", "The Unthinkable Revolution in Iran", and "Roots of Revolution" give us political social, and economic ideas about the Iranian Revolution in 1979.

BP British oil company was the first Iranian oil revenue since the discovery of oil and the company was using the south of the country for producing the oil. Since the BP was in the south of Iran the city named Abadan which is located in Khuzestan Province was the main city for producing that oil for both countries. Sadly, a bigger proportion of the profit from oil was given to the British institution and the rest 15 percent was dedicated to Iran. Obviously, this was so unfair to the Iranian Republic because they were getting paid 10-15 million pounds sterling. There is not enough open information on the Iran Hostage Crisis as it is said that during the revolution Americans did not experience very severe situations such as death. The most notable thing that included the Americans was the American hostages that were taken from Iranian students. In total, there were 52 employees who had to survive 444 days until they were rescued. None of them was dead at that time and were returned home safely by Iranian police officers but that hostage was itself a nightmare for the Americans.

Discussion. The information that has been found so far shows that these two nations could have been the greatest allies in history unless they broke the relationship because of the intervention of the British authorities. This research figured out that if it was not the intervention of the two big characters the global situation might seem quite stable at present. With the help of legal and trustworthy sources, the research found out that if it was not for the British institution that did not want to share its profit with Iran it is more likely that the Iranian revolution also might not have happened. However, it is still possible that these two big characters can begin having diplomatic

relationships again. First and foremost this study concluded that the recent sanctions imposed by the US have to be eased by the government such as reducing Iran's oil export capability and preventing its economy from growing simultaneously. And all individuals should learn to forget about the past as with these memories there is not a single reasonable action to take. After that, for the population to start contact with each other getting a visa for both countries should be at a quite normal level then it is really difficult.

Conclusion. As mentioned above this research mainly focused on two main issues that changed the two superpowers historical relations. In short via such kind of covert operations and tensions, the countries had to experience severe political, economic, and social problems at the time. This article concluded that the two main characters that are United States of America and the Islamic Republic of Iran can not be blamed for their actions. Because the Iranian population itself and the government just desired to nationalize their own natural resources and as for the US the British authorities made them start having an interest in other nations' natural materials. In the long run, it is possible that research might be conducted about the role of the US and Iran in the Israel and Palestine war since in the Middle East except Iran none of the other countries dare to claim war against Israel knowing that the US is the main supporter and ally of this country.

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